

Emotional Intelligence and Conflict Resolution in University Students: The Moderating Effect of the Need for Power

Bimba Dissanayake¹, Sabina Valente^{2,3}, Thilakshi Kodagoda⁴

¹ Wayamba University of Sri Lanka, Kuliypitiya, Sri Lanka

² CARE - Research Center on Health and Social Sciences, Portalegre Polytechnic University, Portalegre, Portugal

³ Research Center in Education and Psychology, University of Évora, Évora, Portugal

⁴ University of Colombo, Colombo, Sri Lanka

**Sri Lanka
Portugal**

*Correspondencia: Sabina Valente. ESECS-IPP, Praça da República, 23-25. 7300-109 Portalegre. Portugal.
E-mail: svalente@ipportalegre.pt*

© Universidad de Almería and Ilustre Colegio Oficial de la Psicología de Andalucía Oriental (Spain)

Abstract

Introduction. Emotional intelligence and motivation are considered antecedent variables in conflict. Studies show the isolated impact of emotional intelligence on conflict and motivation on conflict, but the integrative impact of emotional intelligence and the need for power on the selection of a conflict resolution style is unknown. Consequently, this study aims to fill this gap and examine how the need for power moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and the dominant conflict resolution style.

Method. A questionnaire-based survey was conducted with 388 Sri Lankan university students ($M_{age}=22$). It used simple and moderated multiple regression analysis to evaluate the moderating impact and level of interaction of the need for power on the nexus between emotional intelligence and dominating styles.

Results. The results show a positive correlation between emotional intelligence and dominance style. They also provide new evidence on how the need for power moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and dominance style for conflict resolution in university students.

Discussion and Conclusion. The study provides new evidence about how the need for power moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and dominating conflict resolution style in university students.

Keywords: emotional intelligence, conflict resolution, need for power, university students

Resumen

Introducción. La inteligencia emocional y la motivación se consideran variables antecedentes del conflicto. Los estudios muestran el impacto individual de la inteligencia emocional en el conflicto y de la motivación en el conflicto, pero se desconoce el impacto integrador de la inteligencia emocional y la necesidad de poder en la selección de un estilo de resolución de conflictos. En consecuencia, este estudio pretende llenar este vacío y examinar cómo la necesidad de poder modera la relación entre la inteligencia emocional y el estilo de resolución de conflictos dominante.

Método. Se llevó a cabo la investigación basada en un cuestionario con una muestra de 388 estudiantes universitarios de Sri Lanka ($M_{edad} = 22$). Se utilizó un análisis de regresión múltiple simple y moderado para evaluar el impacto moderador y el nivel de interacción de la necesidad de poder en el nexo entre la inteligencia emocional y los estilos dominantes.

Resultados. Los resultados muestran una correlación positiva entre la inteligencia emocional y el estilo de dominancia. También aporta nuevas evidencias sobre cómo la necesidad de poder modera la relación entre la inteligencia emocional y el estilo de dominación para la resolución de conflictos en estudiantes universitarios.

Discusión y Conclusion: El estudio aporta nuevas pruebas sobre cómo la necesidad de poder modera la relación entre la inteligencia emocional y el estilo dominante de resolución de conflictos en estudiantes universitarios.

Palabras clave: inteligencia emocional, resolución de conflictos, necesidad de poder, estudiantes universitarios

Introduction

The social and economic crisis has created new problems and potential sources of conflict in all spheres of Sri Lankan society (Hadad-Zervos, 2023), and education is no exception. So, conflict is a problem for every organization, including universities (Firman et al., 2022). Thus, it is common in the Sri Lankan university system to encounter recurrent conflicts. Conflicts are frequent among students and between staff and students, which leads Sri Lankan university students to disbelieve and adopt a hostile approach to conflict resolution (Ruberu, 2003).

Studies indicate that different types of conflicts occur among higher education students. These include instances of theft, fights, examination malpractice, corruption, disobedience to teachers and university rules and regulations, and participation in student unrest (Bashar et al. 2020). The main conflicts that occur in Sri Lanka universities are the regular student protests, university closures brought on by student unrest, postponements of exams and admissions as a result of students skipping classes, and other student-related issues that have caused severe issues for the university administration. So, student conflicts in Sri Lankan universities are influenced by various factors. Communication gaps between students and management, inadequate facilities, and leadership issues are major drivers of conflicts (Akpaprep & Akpaprep, 2024). Ragging, a form of initiation ritual, is prevalent in Sri Lankan universities and is associated with student politics (Gunatilaka, 2019). Despite its negative consequences, it is perceived as an expression of power, a way to address social inequalities, and a means to bond students (Wickramasinghe et al., 2022). Student activism, deeply embedded in the system, is often labeled a political matter and ignored by authorities (Kumari & Fernando, 2021).

As a result, it has grown from being an intra-university problem to a national one (Akpaprep & Akpaprep, 2024; Wickramasinghe et al., 2022). University students are known to be the finest intellect among Sri Lanka's advanced-level students and are the prospected prominent drivers of the country. These favoured few are the best of the nation, with all the potential to lead the country to new horizons (Hennayake, 2008). In this sequence, Weeramunda (2008) strongly suggests that this requires multi-dimensional solutions mainly focusing on methods of conflict resolution as the violence and indiscipline in the universities have multiple causes. Thus, preventing conflicts in an educational institution is a crucial task that must be solved (Zolkin et al., 2020).

In human society, differences in characteristics lead to disagreements among individuals and consequently advance into conflict, eventually becoming an inseparable component of human life (Valente et al., 2020). Thus, conflict could be viewed as a natural consequence of diversity occurring due to cognition and social interaction aspects of human behavior, which have a certain appearance in the social context (Valente et al., 2020). The conflict, initially viewed as a negative phenomenon that must be avoided at any cost (Pondy, 1967), is currently perceived as having several positive characteristics as long as it is well managed (De Dreu & Van de Vliert, 1997). In this sequence, conflict also presents a significant impact on development at a personal, interpersonal, and group level (Doğan, 2016). Therefore, efficient conflict management strategies can reduce the negative impacts of conflict, helping to create a healthy climate for improving interpersonal relationships (Valente et al., 2022). Predominantly, conflict management strategies determine whether the outcomes are constructive or destructive (Park & Antonioni, 2007).

Rahim's (2002) conflict management model describes the strategies used to manage conflicts based on two dimensions: concern for oneself and concern for others. Concern for self refers to the degree to which individuals aim to satisfy their concerns in conflict management processes. In turn, the concern for others dimension refers to the degree of care about the others involved in the conflict. The result, combined with the two dimensions of Rahim's model, are five strategies (i.e., integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising) for handling interpersonal conflict (Rahim, 2002). These strategies correspond to the attitudes presented to face conflicts (Valente et al., 2020). Domination means a high level of preoccupation with oneself and a low level of preoccupation with others (Rahim, 2002). Thus, by using this strategy, they seek to achieve their goals, feeling that the conflict can be controlled through domination and suppressing the needs and expectations of others (Valente & Lourenço, 2020). This strategy is characterised by high assertiveness and a lack of cooperation (Medina & Munduate, 2005).

Among the variables that influence the choice of different conflict management strategies, emotional intelligence (EI) stands out (Valente & Lourenço, 2022). The theoretical Mayer and Salovey (1997) EI model explain the processing of emotional information through a system of four capacities organized into levels, defining EI as "the ability to perceive accurately, appraise, and express emotion; the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they

facilitate thought; the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth” (Mayer & Salovey, 1997, p. 10). Thus, EI is a person’s intelligence to control and adapt rationally to his setting (Kushtyarini, 2020).

Human conflict does not exist without emotions (Jones, 2000). So, EI is an antecedent of conflict (Shih & Susanto, 2010). Also, Bodtker and Jameson (2001) favorably argue that if a person is to be in conflict, he must be emotionally charged. Consequently, conflict is an emotionally created and emotionally driven process (Valente et al., 2022), and proper identification of the emotions involved in a conflict process exposes the opportunities to orchestrate conflict management productively (Jordan & Troth, 2004).

EI rationality is suppressed when people adopt a dominant conflict resolution style, and high-EI people have shown a lesser tendency to select the dominant style (Chen et al., 2019; Pandey et al., 2015; Valente & Lourenço, 2020). The use of a dominant style of conflict resolution varies with gender and the EI level of managers, i.e., female employees are more likely to adopt the dominant style when confronted with a conflict with subordinates. In contrast, male employees adopt the dominant style when handling conflicts with their peers (Chen et al., 2019). Another study affirms that in classroom conflict management, teachers who tend to have more EI rarely use a dominant style (Valente & Lourenço, 2020).

Motivation is the effort a person makes to pursue a goal and claim it is directly related to job performance and worker or employee satisfaction (Widarko & Anwarodin, 2022). It explains an individual's intensity, direction, and persistence of effort toward achieving a goal. An important aspect of predicting the causes of behavior is having a thorough understanding of human motivation. Three motivational factors that influence behavior are the need for achievement, the need for power (nPow), and the need for affiliation. According to McClelland (1987), a person’s desire to influence others is known as nPow (Moon et al., 2022), and the extent to which how strongly a person wishes to attain a dominant position in a group will determine the competitive relationships among them (Chun & Choi, 2014).

Even though there is research conducted to test the impact of EI on conflict (e.g., Chan et al., 2014; Khosravi et al., 2020; Rahim et al., 2002; Valente & Lourenço, 2022) and motivation on conflict (e.g., Bell & Blakeney, 1977; Konul & Şebnem, 2021; Mrayyan et al.,

2008; Sorenson et al., 1999), in the literature review carried out, no studies were found on the integrative impact of EI and nPow on the selection of the dominant conflict resolution style. A Rahim et al. (2001) study established that power bases are a significant decisive factor in the selection of conflict resolution styles and suggested future studies to investigate the link among EI, power, and conflict resolution styles. However, little is known about how university students' EI level and nPow motivation drive the dominant conflict resolution style. This study addressed the problem: "How does nPow moderate the relationship between EI and dominating conflict resolution style?"

So, to capture the underlying triggers which cause the conflict, a look into the multi-dimensional influence of EI and the nPow on dominating conflict resolution style among Sri Lanka university undergraduates is deemed necessary. To understand the interplay among these concepts, it is essential to understand their interconnections. EI corresponds to how people identify, perceive, understand and regulate their emotions and those of others (Mayer & Salovey, 1997), which is essential in conflict resolution (Valente & Lourenço, 2020). Given that conflict is often influenced by an individual's ability to empathize, communicate, and regulate emotions, EI plays a significant role in defining people's resolution style when resolving a conflict. Meanwhile, the nPow, a person's underlying motive to control and influence others, would define how one leverages emotional skills and resolves disputes (Carvalho & Conde, 2024; Moon et al., 2022). Exploring these variables together could better understand how EI impacts conflict resolution styles and how the nPow shapes these interactions.

Objectives and Hypotheses

The main aim of this study is to investigate how nPow moderates the relationship between EI and dominant conflict resolution style of university students. Based upon prior studies, the proposed hypotheses were: H1) a positive and statistically significant relationship is expected between university students' EI and dominant conflict resolution style, and H2) nPow is expected to moderate the relationship between EI and dominant conflict resolution style in university students.

Method

Participants

The study design was descriptive-correlational with a non-experimental cross-sectional design. Using non-probabilistic methods (convenience sampling), the sample included 397 university students from Sri Lanka state-owned universities. After eliminating nine datasets as outliers, the final sample size was 388 students ($M_{age} = 22$). Of the participants, 62 were men and 326 were women. So, the majority of the students were female (84.0%), and a significant fraction (80.4%) were in their 3rd (39.7%) and 4th (40.7%) academic years, respectively. The highest number of respondents represent Wayamba University of Sri Lanka (33.5%), and most of them followed management-related degree programs (64.3%; Bachelor of Science in Management: 48.5%; Bachelor of Business Management: 12.4%; Bachelor of Commerce: 3.4%). A summary of the sample's attributes is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Sample profile of the respondents*

Variable	Category	Frequency	
		<i>n</i>	%
Gender	Male	62	16.0
	Female	326	84.0
Year	Year 1	11	2.8
	Year 2	65	16.8
	Year 3	154	39.7
	Year 4	158	40.7
Degree	Agriculture	56	14.4
	Bachelor of Arts	10	2.6
	Bachelor of Business Administration	17	4.4
	Bachelor of Business Management	48	12.4
	Bachelor of Commerce	13	3.4
	Bachelor of Science – Science Stream	42	10.8
	Bachelor of Science – Management Stream	188	48.5
	Information & Communication Technology	9	2.3
	Other	5	1.3

Instruments

Socio-demographic and academic data questionnaire: socio-demographic items included age and gender, and the academic profile included academic year, university, and degree program.

Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS; Wong & Law, 2002): consisted of 16 items, and the answers were obtained on a Likert scale with 5 options, from 1 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*) to measure the EI perception, distributed among four subscales: self-emotional appraisal, 4 items; ($\alpha = .65$; e.g., I have a good sense of why I feel certain feelings most of the time); other emotional appraisal, 4 items ($\alpha = .60$; e.g., I always know my friends' emotions from their behaviour); use of emotion, 4 items ($\alpha = .69$; e.g., I am a self-motivating person); and regulation of emotion, 4 items ($\alpha = .74$; e.g., I have good control of my emotions). The study's overall scale has an internal consistency of $\alpha = .79$.

Rahim's Organizational Conflict Inventory-II (ROCI-II-C; Rahim, 1983): comprises 28 items, rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (*totally disagree*) to 5 (*totally agree*). Items are distributed among five subscales: integrating, obliging, dominating, avoiding, and compromising. For this study, only the subscale referring to the dominant conflict resolution style was applied, 5 items (e.g., I use my authority to make a decision in my favor). The Cronbach's α for the current sample was adequate ($\alpha = .72$).

Unified Motive Scales (UMS; Schönbrodt & Gerstenberg, 2012): consisted of 30 items to distribute among three subscales: achievement, nPow, and affiliation. The measures were on a 6-point Likert scale of 0 (*strongly disagree*) to 5 (*strongly agree*). For this study, only the subscale referring to the nPow was applied, 10 items (e.g., I try to control others rather than allowing them to control me). For the current study, the Cronbach's α was acceptable ($\alpha = .81$).

Procedure

The study's inclusion criteria, which were based on the choice of participating universities and their courses, were chosen because they have a higher rate of student conflicts than other degree programs (e.g., engineering and medicine) and other higher education institutions in Sri Lanka, which qualifies them for this study. The ethical standards of the institutional and national research committees were followed in every procedure that was carried out. The research complied with the 2013 Helsinki Declaration and the American Psychological Association's ethical guidelines. The study was cross-sectional since data was only collected at a given time horizon, and the respondents received the questionnaires through Google Forms. Consequently, before completing the questionnaires, the participants were

made aware of the study's objectives and assured of following ethical protocols, which included anonymity, response confidentiality, and voluntary participation. Then, a question about wanting to participate in the study was posed to them. They were permitted to proceed with the online questionnaire after selecting "yes."

Data Analysis

The quantitative nature of the study involved using a range of statistical methods for data analysis. The data obtained through the application of self-report instruments were analysed with the SPSS29 program (Arbuckle, 2022). Firstly, data analysis was initiated with data entry and examination of missing values. Therefore, the data set was screened for missing values, and since it did not contain any missing values, the researcher proceeded ahead without needing to treat the missing values. Subsequently, the data were tested to check whether any critical outliers were using Boxplots and Mahalanobis distance (D2) estimates, effectively detecting outliers. The cases with a probability less than or equal to .001 were eliminated from the datasheet to maintain a more representative sample.

Afterwards, a preliminary analysis was conducted to ensure the completeness and accuracy of the data and to test for normality, linearity, homogeneity of variance, and multicollinearity of the data set. In the next phase, the validity and reliability were tested to ensure the credibility of the results. Cronbach's α test was conducted to check the reliability of the responses before conducting the descriptive and correlation analyses of the study. According to Field (2013), Cronbach's α are $\alpha \geq .90$: excellent (very high reliability); $.80 \leq \alpha < .90$: good (high reliability); $.70 \leq \alpha < .80$: acceptable (moderate reliability); $.60 \leq \alpha < .70$: questionable (low reliability); $.50 \leq \alpha < .60$: poor (very low reliability); $\alpha < .50$: unacceptable (not reliable). EI, nPow, and dominating style report sound internal reliability with Cronbach's α values of .70 and above. Secondly, descriptive analysis was carried out (means, standard deviations, and internal consistency of variables) In addition, associations between variables were analysed using Pearson's bivariate correlation analysis. For Pearson's linear correlation (r), it was considered that values below .200 indicate a very weak association, values between .200 - .399 indicate a weak association, values between .400 - .699 indicate a moderate association, values between .700 - .899 indicate a high association and values between .900 - 1 indicate a very high association (Hair et al., 2019). The Pearson correlations were performed to provide a deeper analysis of the direction and strength of the nexus between EI perception, nPow, and the dominant conflict resolution style.

In third place, simple regression analysis [coefficient of determination (R^2), statistical significance (p -value), regression coefficient (β), standard error (SE) and t -statistic] was used to examine the direction and degree of influence of the relationship between the variables. Finally, moderated multiple regression analysis [R^2 and change in R^2 (ΔR^2), p -value, β , SE , F -test for overall model significance] was used to evaluate the moderating effect and level of interaction of nPow on the nexus between EI perception and the dominant conflict resolution style. According to Field (2013), $R^2 = 1$: perfect model fit, explains 100% of the variance; $.75 \leq R^2 < 1$: strong model fit, explains a large proportion of variance; $.50 \leq R^2 < .75$: moderate model fit, explains a reasonable proportion of variance; $0 \leq R^2 < .50$: Weak model fit, explains little variance; $R^2 = 0$: the model does not explain any variance. About ΔR^2 , this reflects the improvement in variance explained due to moderation; a small but significant change in R^2 can still indicate meaningful moderation, and a significant ΔR^2 suggests that the moderator contributes meaningfully to explaining the variance. A significant F -test ($p < .05$) indicates that the model with the moderation effect is a better fit than a model without it.

Results

Table 2 shows that undergraduates are reported to have a fairly higher level of EI with a mean value of $M = 5.47$ ($SD = .584$). The group was driven by power motives and reported an average value of $M = 3.55$ ($SD = .658$). The dominating style was reported to have a positive tendency with a mean value of $M = 3.59$ ($SD = .599$). Further, Table 2 indicates a slightly weak but significant correlation between EI and dominating style ($r = .188$, $p < .01$), EI and nPow ($r = .140$, $p < .01$). However, nPow reported to have a moderate impact on dominating style ($r = .488$, $p < .01$).

Table 2. Correlation matrix of the relationships among EI, nPow, and dominating style

	M	SD	(1)	(2)	(3)
EI (1)	5.47	0.584	-		
Dominating Style (2)	3.59	0.599	.188**	-	
nPow (3)	3.55	0.658	.140**	.488**	-

Note. EI = Emotional Intelligence; nPow = Need for Power; ** $p < .01$

The results of Table 3 show the simple regression model used to test the hypothesis that EI significantly impacts the dominant conflict resolution style. The results revealed a significant relationship between EI and dominating style ($\beta = .191, p < .001$).

Table 3. *Simple regression analysis*

Model	B	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	2.545	9.018	.000
EI	0.191	3.720	.000
R	0.186***		
R ²	0.035***		
F	13.838		

Note. EI = Emotional Intelligence; ** $p < .01$

The regression results are shown in Table 4. A significant relationship exists between EI and dominating style [$R^2 = .035, F(1.386) = 13.838, p < .001$].

Table 4. *Hierarchical regression*

Variable	Model 1	Model 2
(Constant)	1.715 (116.010)	4.126 (116.010)
EI	0.091* (2.231)	-0.353 (-1.867)
nPow	0.394*** (10.043)	-0.319 (-1.067)
EI_X_nPow	-	0.131** (2.406)
F	58.678	41.535
R ²	0.234***	0.245***
ΔR^2	-	.011**

Note. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; *** $p < .001$; EI = Emotional Intelligence; nPow = Need for Power

As shown in Table 4, the model indices in steps 1 [$F(2.385) = 58.678, p < .001$], and 2 [$F(1.384) = 41.535, p < .001$] are statistically significant. The model 1 and 2 explain a variance of 23.4% [$R^2 = .234, F(2.385) = 58.678, p < .001$], 24.5% [$R^2 = .245, F(1.384) = 41.535, p < .001$] in the dominating style respectively. The statistical scores of the EI ($\beta =$

091, $p < .05$), and nPow ($\beta = .394$, $p < .001$) in model 1 were significant but with the introduction of the interaction term ($\beta = .131$, $p < .01$) in model 2, EI ($\beta = -.353$, $p > .05$), nPow ($\beta = -.319$, $p > .05$) became insignificant. With the introduction of the interaction construct, the change of the R^2 value was significant ($\Delta R^2 = .011$, $p < .05$) indicating that there is significant moderation between EI and nPow on dominating style ($\beta = .131$, $p < .01$).

Discussion and conclusion

The findings revealed a significant and positive relationship between university students' EI and dominating conflict resolution style, supporting the H1, as in the Chane et al. (2014) study. This may be because the study considered the conflict arising among fellow students, and due to the two parties sharing the same status level. Although the dominating style is generally seen as opposed to the collaborative nature often associated with high EI (Valente & Lourenço, 2020), students with higher EI may justifiably resort to this style in certain circumstances. This may be because they can quickly assess situations, are more focused on protecting their goals, and manage their time and resources more effectively. Students with high EI are generally better able to regulate their emotions, even in stressful or tense situations such as conflicts (Partido & Colon, 2023). Thus, they often have a problem-solving mentality, focusing on resolving the issues behind conflicts. It's worth noting that the domination style is helpful when a quick decision has to be made, when the conflict is trivial, and even when something challenging to accept is being dealt with (Rahim, 2002). In addition, the ability to control their emotions and understand those of others can allow them to use domination strategically and control without necessarily causing more significant damage to relationships.

Therefore, and even though EI is often associated with more collaborative and cooperative conflict resolution styles, the results of the present study, a positive and statistically significant relationship between higher education students with higher EI and the dominant conflict resolution style, can be justified due to students with more EI may have strong confidence in their ability to quickly analyse situations and make effective decisions. Thus, they may opt for the domination style in conflict situations, believing that its quick resolution will benefit the group or situation. On the other hand, students with higher EI are generally more aware of their goals and the consequences of not achieving them. When goals are seen as crit-

ical or essential, students with high EI may use the domination style to ensure their interests prevail, especially if they realise that collaboration could jeopardise important results.

EI also involves assessing the situation and choosing the most appropriate conflict resolution style (Valente & Lourenço, 2020). So, emotionally intelligent students can recognise that, in certain circumstances, the domination style can be the most effective, such as in crises, tight deadlines, or situations where a quick decision is needed, and the consensus is difficult to achieve.

Considering H2, the same was proven, as the results show that nPow moderates the relationship between EI and the dominant conflict resolution style. Results support evidence to prove a significant moderation between EI and nPow on dominating styles in university students. Thus, university students show a high level of concern for themselves in their academic lives, which is associated with a tendency to influence others about their needs, which are considered superior to those of their peers. Therefore, when using a dominating strategy in a conflict with a colleague, the aim is to find a satisfactory agreement for themselves. This strategy demonstrates authority by ignoring others' needs and perspectives (Rahim, 2002).

Thus, according to the present study results, it is possible to affirm that the nPow works as a fundamental moderating factor in the relationship between EI and the dominant conflict resolution style among higher education students. The nPow, an individual's desire to control, influence, or dominate others (Moon et al., 2022), can shape how EI manifests itself in conflict resolution. For example, students with a high nPow may use their EI differently than those with a low nPow. For students with a high nPow, EI can be leveraged to manipulate or assert dominance during conflicts. They may use their awareness of others' emotions and social skills to persuade, control, or impose their perspective, gravitating toward more dominant conflict styles (e.g., competitive or assertive behaviors). On the other hand, students with a low nPow may use EI in a more cooperative or collaborative way, focusing on finding mutually beneficial outcomes rather than exerting control. This group may lean toward integrating or accommodating conflict styles, using their EI to promote harmony and understanding rather than dominance.

Another reason to justify these results may be related to the fact that students with a high nPow may perceive conflicts as opportunities to assert authority or gain control (Schmid

et al., 2015), thus forcing them to resolve conflicts to reinforce their dominance. In this context, EI may allow them to read others' emotions better but channel this understanding into strategies that serve their power motives, which may not necessarily involve compromise or collaboration. In contrast, students with a lower nPow may perceive conflicts as situations that require emotional regulation and cooperation. In these cases, EI would reduce tensions and reach equitable resolutions, reinforcing collaborative or compromise styles.

EI includes regulating emotions in oneself and others (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). However, a high nPow can change how students use emotional regulation. Thus, those driven by power may focus on controlling the emotional reactions of others to maintain the upper hand in conflicts. Which can develop a strong tendency towards dominant styles in conflict resolution. EI typically encourages the application of conflict resolution styles that value understanding and cooperation (Valente & Lourenço, 2020). However, the present study results indicate that when the nPow is high, students may experience cognitive dissonance where their EI is replaced by their desire for dominance. This creates a moderating effect, where the nPow shifts the balance between using EI for genuine resolution and using it as a tool to assert dominance. Thus, students with high EI, but also with a high nPow, adopt dominant styles in the presence of conflicts, using their EI more strategically.

Study's Theoretical and Practical Contributions

Both theoretical and practical implications arise from the study's findings. Regarding theoretical implications, results demonstrate that nPow defines the relationship between EI and dominant conflict resolution styles. So, the nPow overpowers the EI and directs a person to select the dominant conflict resolution style. Regarding the practical implications, in higher education, where students often engage in group projects, leadership roles, and peer interactions, the nPow becomes a significant factor influencing conflict resolution. Thus, students with high EI and a high nPow can dominate group discussions or decision-making processes, to steer the results in their favour. Even though the students choose a dominant style, their high EI allows them to use better understanding and emotion regulation during conflict to lessen its negative effects (Valente & Lourenço, 2020). To address these issues, strategies such as strengthening more emotive communication, involving students in decision-making and providing effective institutional leadership are recommended. In addition, adopting fair, respectful and humanistic approaches, along with two-way communication and flexible

mechanisms, can help deal smoothly with student activism (Akpapere & Akpapere, 2019; Kumari & Fernando, 2021) and thus reduce existing conflicts in higher education in Sri Lanka.

Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research

While the study's findings are promising, it is important to consider certain limitations. Even though power bases play a significant role in the choice of conflict resolution styles, as noted by Rahim et al. (2001), no research on the combined influence of EI and nPow on the choice of the dominant conflict resolution style was located. Therefore, it is recommended that future research look into the relationship between EI, nPow, and dominant styles in conflict resolution. Also, it is important to understand the moderating role of the nPow to explain the variability in the way EI affects other conflict resolution strategies in different student profiles. Second, self-report measures may lead to results related to collective method bias. Furthermore, objective data gathered from student interviews, such as the frequency with which students use the dominance style to settle disputes with coworkers and the reasons behind their decision to do so, must be added to the self-report measures in the description of the dominance strategy used for conflict management. It should be noted that it also makes sense to question students according to some variables, such as the level of education they attend and the scientific area of their academic training so that the analysis of results can meet some contextual variables. Or use solely a qualitative research methodology in future studies to evaluate the variables under study. Another limitation is related to the fact that the sample includes university students from a single country. So, the results may differ in other countries with different cultural backgrounds. It is therefore recommended that the study be reproduced in other cultural contexts. Cross-cultural investigations are recommended to determine how nPow moderates the relationship between university students' perception of EI and the dominant style for resolving conflicts with peers. It is also suggested that future studies should include other personal and organizational variables that can influence university students' nPow and moderate the relationship between EI and conflict resolution styles.

This study aimed to determine how nPow influences the association between students' EI and dominant conflict resolution style. The study provides new evidence about how nPow moderates the relationship between EI and dominating conflict resolution style in university students from Sri Lanka. In conclusion, this study shows that nPow moderates the relationship between EI and dominating conflict resolution style in university students. Thus, students with a high nPow tend to channel their EI towards dominance and control in conflict with

peers. So, given this study's results, it is suggested that the university system introduce programs to elevate the students' level of EI so that they can be more understanding of others' emotions and regulate their emotions effectively. Also, the need for training in conflict management for Sri Lanka university students is suggested. In addition, the system should encourage team achievement, simulate group learning, and increase students' affiliation with each other, so that they not only focus on their self-wins, i.e., the nPow, but also on collective achievement, which can lead to better handling of conflict situations.

References

- Afzalur Rahim, M., Antonioni, D., & Psenicka, C. (2001). A structural equations model of leader power, subordinates' styles of handling conflict, and job performance. *International journal of conflict management*, 12(3), 191–211. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022855>
- Akparep, Y., & Akparep, A. Y. (2024). Effectiveness in adversity: unpacking strategies for student-management conflict resolution (1999-2009) at the university for development studies. *Journal of Current Research and Review*, 15(1), 26–41. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10572852>
- Arbuckle, J. L. (2022). *IBM®, SPSS®, Amos™ 29 User's Guide*. IBM
- Bashar, S. I., Gatawa, M. I., Musa, B., Aziz, N. A., & Hassan, A. (2020). Students' indiscipline in higher educational institutions of Sokoto state: The forms, causes and management approaches. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research*, 6(12). <https://doi.org/10.46654/ij.24889849.a61245>
- Bell, E. C., & Blakeney, R. N. (1977). Personality correlates of conflict resolution modes. *Human Relations*, 30, 849–857. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001872677703000907>
- Bodtker, A., & Jameson, J. (2001). Emotion in conflict formation and its transformation: application to organizational conflict management. *The International Journal of Conflict Management*, 12(3), 259–275. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022858>
- Carvalho, J. M., & Conde, A. (2024). Individual power in human motivation: review and theoretical perspective. *Acta Psychologica*, 249, 104452. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actpsy.2024.104452>

- Chan, J. C., Sit, E. N., & Lau, W. M. (2014). Conflict management styles, emotional intelligence and implicit theories of personality of nursing students: A cross-sectional study. *Nurse Education Today*, 34(6), 934–939. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.10.012>
- Chen, H., Xu, X., & Phillips, P. (2019). Emotional intelligence and conflict management styles. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 2(3), 458–470. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOA-11-2017-1272>
- Chun, J. S., & Choi, J. N. (2014). Members' needs, intragroup conflict, and group performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 99(3), 437–450. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036363>
- De Dreu, C. K. W., & Van de Vliert, E. (1997). *Using conflict in organizations*. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Declaration of Helsinki (2013). Ethical principles for medical research involving human subjects. *JAMA*, 310(20), 2191–2194. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.281053>
- Doğan, S. (2016). Conflicts management model in school: A mixed design study. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 5(2), 200–219. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jel.v5n2p200>
- Field, A. (2013). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics*. Sage Publications Ltd.
- Firman, E., Anra, Y., & Setiawan, B. (2022). Influence of interpersonal conflict and social norms towards organizational conflict and lecturer occupational stress. *International Journal of Instruction*, 15(4), 645–666. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2022.15435a>
- Gunatilaka, H. (2019). Ragging; Its evolution and effects: a literature review with a special reference to Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, III(X), 92–99.
- Hadad-Zervos, F. (2023, October). Sri Lanka Development Update 2023. *The World Bank*. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/srilanka/publication/sri-lanka-development-update-2023>
- Hair, J. F., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Black, W. C. (2019). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (8th ed.). Pearson Prentice.
- Hennayake, S. (2008, November 20). *The Fundamental Threat to Sri Lankan University Education*. Retrieved June 16, 2023, from <http://www.asiantribune.com/?q=node/14294>
- Jones, T. (2000). *The Language of Conflict and Resolution*. Sage Publications Ltd.

- Jordan, P. J., & Troth, A. C. (2004). Managing emotions during team problem solving: Emotional intelligence and conflict resolution. *Human Performance*, 17(2), 195–218. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327043hup1702_4
- Khosravi, P., Rezvani, A., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2020). Emotional intelligence: A preventive strategy to manage destructive influence of conflict in large scale projects. *International Journal of Project Management*, 38(1), 36–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2019.11.001>
- Konul, M., & Şebnem, G. K. (2021). Fuzzy-Logic Modelling of the relationship between work motivation and conflict solving skills of academicians regarding life balance model of positive psychotherapy. In *14th International Conference on Theory and Application of Fuzzy Systems and Soft Computing–ICAFS-2020 14*, 426-432. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-64058-3_53
- Kumari, M. D., & Fernando, R. L. S. (2021). Dealing smoothly with student activism: reflections of activists and administrators in Sri Lankan state university system. *Muallim Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 85-99. <https://doi.org/10.33306/mjssh/141>
- Kustyarini, K. (2020). Self-efficacy and emotional quotient in mediating active learning effect on students' learning outcome. *International Journal of Instruction*, 13(2), 663–676. <https://doi.org/10.29333/iji.2020.13245a>
- Mayer, J. D., & Salovey, P. (1997). What is Emotional Intelligence? In P. Salovey, & J. Sluyter (Eds.), *Emotional development and emotional intelligence: Educational implications* (pp. 3–31). Basic Books.
- McClelland, D. C. (1987). *Human motivation*. Cambridge University Press Archive.
- Medina, F. J., & Munduate, L. (2005). Evaluación de la gestión del conflicto. In L. Munduate, & F. J. Medina (Eds.), *Gestión del Conflicto, Negociación y Mediación* (pp. 73–90). Ediciones Pirámide.
- Moon, B., Lee, N. M.-H., & Bourdage, J. S. (2022). Personalized and socialized need for power: Distinct relations to employee traits and behaviors. *Canadian Journal of Behavioural Science / Revue Canadienne des Sciences du Comportement*, 54(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cbs0000279>
- Mrayyan, M. T., Modallal, R., Awamreh, K., Atoum, M., Abdullah, M., & Suliman, S. (2008). Readiness of organizations for change, motivation and conflict-handling inten-

- tions: Senior nursing students' perceptions. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 8(2), 120–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2007.04.001>
- Pandey, S., Sajjanapu, S., & Sangwan, G. (2015). Study on effect of emotional intelligence on conflict resolution style. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(6), 1–11. <https://doi.org/8.71.10.17485/ijst/2015/v8iS6/71215>
- Park, H., & Antonioni, D. (2007). Personality, reciprocity, and strength of conflict resolution strategy. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 41(1), 110–125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2006.03.003>
- Partido, B., & Colon, E. (2023). Emotional intelligence as a predictor of conflict management styles among dental hygiene students. *International Journal of Dental Hygiene*, 22(2), 277–283. <https://doi.org/10.1111/idh.12717>.
- Pondy, L. R. (1967). Organizational conflict: Concepts and models. *Administrative science quarterly*, 13, 296–320. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2391553>
- Rahim, M. (2002). Toward a theory on managing organizational conflict. *The International Journal of Conflict Management*, 13(3), 206–235. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022874>
- Rahim, M. A. (1983). A measure of styles of handling interpersonal conflict. *Academy of Management Journal*, 26(2), 368–376. <https://doi.org/10.2307/255985>
- Rahim, M., Psenicka, C., Polychroniou, P., Zhao, J. H., Yu, C. S., Anita Chan, K., et al. (2002). A model of emotional intelligence and conflict management strategies: A study in seven countries. *The International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 10(4), 302–326. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb028955>
- Ruberu, R. (2003, January 30). *Indiscipline in Sri Lankan Universities*. Retrieved August 1, 2017, from <http://www.island.lk/2003/01/30/featur01.html>
- Schmid, P., Kleiman, T., & Amodio, D. (2015). Power effects on cognitive control: turning conflict into action. *Journal of Experimental Psychology. General*, 144(3), 655–663. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000068>
- Schönbrodt, F. D., & Gerstenberg, F. X. (2012). An IRT analysis of motive questionnaires: The Unified Motive Scales. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 6, 725–742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrp.2012.08.010>

- Shih, H. A., & Susanto, E. (2010). Conflict management styles, emotional intelligence, and job performance in public organizations. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 21(2), 147–168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10444061011037387>
- Sorenson, R. L., Morse, E. A., & Savage, G. T. (1999). A test of the motivations underlying choice of conflict strategies in the dual-concern model. *International Journal of Conflict Management*, 10(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022817>
- Valente, S., & Lourenço, A. A. (2020). Conflict in the classroom: How teachers' emotional intelligence influences conflict management? *Frontiers in Education*, 5(5). <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2020.00005>
- Valente, S., & Lourenço, A. A. (2022). Inteligência emocional e gestão de conflito na interação pedagógica. *Revista de Estudos e Investigación en Psicología y Educación*, 9, 181–192. <https://doi.org/10.17979/reipe.2022.9.0.8900>
- Valente, S., Lourenço, A. A., & Németh, Z. (2020). School conflicts: Causes and management strategies in classroom relationships. In M. P. Levine (Ed.), *Interpersonal Relationships* (pp. 1–16). IntechOpen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.95395>
- Valente, S., Lourenço, A. A., Dominguez-Lara, S., Derakhshan, A., Németh, Z., & S. Almeida, L. (2022). Teachers' emotion regulation: Implications for classroom conflict management. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 47(8), 18–32. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14221/ajte.2022v47n8.2>
- Wickramasinghe, A., Axemo, P., Essén, B., & Trenholm, J. (2022). Ragging as an expression of power in a deeply divided society; a qualitative study on students perceptions on the phenomenon of ragging at a Sri Lankan university. *PLoS ONE*, 17(7), e0271087. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0271087>
- Weeramunda, A. J. (2008). *Socio Political Impact of Student Violence and Indiscipline in Universities and Tertiary Education Institutes*. National Education Commission
- Widarko, A., & Anwarodin, M. K. (2022). Work motivation and organizational culture on work performance: Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) as mediating variable. *Golden Ratio of Human Resource Management*, 2(2), 123–138. <https://doi.org/10.52970/grhrm.v2i2.207>

Wong, C. S., & Law, K. S. (2002). The effects of leader and follower emotional intelligence on performance and attitude: An exploratory study. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 13(3), 243–274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1048-9843\(02\)00099-1r](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1048-9843(02)00099-1r)

Zolkin, A. L., Kornetov, A. N., Mironchuk, V. A., Giniyatullina, D. R., & Ryabkova, G. V. (2020). Modern pedagogical technologies for prevention of conflicts between students of vocational education institutions. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1691(1), 012228. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1691/1/012228>

Received: 26-05-2024
Accepted: 10-09-2024